

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10205814>

urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:FF80F66F-E33C-470D-9232-3F309A876D3E

New records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) of the Dniester valley (Podilski Tovtry and Dniester Canyon National Nature Parks)

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Krivosheyev, R. E. New records of the short-winged mold beetles (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Pselaphinae) of the Dniester valley (Podilski Tovtry and Dniester Canyon National Nature Parks). — 24 species of the pselaphines were collected in the Dniester River valley within the borders of two national nature parks: Podilsky Tovtry (Khmelnitsky Region) and Dniester Canyon (Ternopil Region) during several expeditions in 2017 and 2023. The species *Euplectus nanus* (Reichenbach, 1816), *Euplectus kirbii kirbii* Denny, 1825, *Batrisodes adnexus* (Hampe, 1863), *Fagniezia impressa* (Panzer, 1805), *Bryaxis ruthenus* (Saulcy, 1877), *Tychus niger* (Paykull, 1800), and *Claviger testaceus* Preyssler, 1790, are new for the Region, and the species *Bythinus acutangulus* Reitter, 1878, and *Pselaphus salonitanus* (Karaman, 1940) are recorded from Ukraine for the first time.

Key words: Ukraine, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Podilski Tovtry, Dniestrovskiy Canyon, new records.

Кривошесев, Р. Є. Нові знахідки жуків-потаємців з долини Дністра (Національні природні парки «Подільські Товтри» та «Дністровський Каньйон»). 24 види потаємців знайдено з долини річки Дністер в межах двох національних природних парків: Подільські Товтри (Хмельницька обл.) та Дністровський Каньйон (Тернопільська обл.) протягом декількох експедицій в 2017 та 2023 рр. Види *Euplectus nanus* (Reichenbach, 1816), *Euplectus kirbii kirbii* Denny, 1825, *Batrisodes adnexus* (Hampe, 1863), *Fagniezia impressa* (Panzer, 1805), *Bryaxis ruthenus* (Saulcy, 1877), *Tychus niger* (Paykull, 1800) та *Claviger testaceus* Preyssler, 1790, вперше відмічено для регіону. Види *Bythinus cutangulus* Reitter, 1878 та *Pselaphus salonitanus* (Karaman, 1940) — вперше знайдено в Україні.

Ключові слова: Україна, Staphylinidae, Pselaphinae, Подільські Товтри, Дністровський Каньйон, нові знахідки.

Introduction

The subfamily Pselaphinae was known to be represented by 126 species of 25 genera in the fauna of Ukraine (Krivosheyev, 2015). In the canyon of the Dniester River and its largest tributaries, several expeditions were conducted from 2012 to 2023 in Khmelnytsky, Ternopil and Vinnytsya Regions. From Ternopil Region so far 7 species have been recorded from the Medobory range (Kubisz et al., 1998), 14 species from Podilski Tovtry National Nature Park (Krivosheyev, 2015), 12 — from Dniester Canyon National Nature Park (Krivosheyev, 2018) and 10 — from Vinnitsya part of Dniester valley (Krivosheyev, 2021). An interesting thermophilic species *Bryaxis chaudoirii* (Chaudoir, 1845), which is found throughout Ukraine along river valleys only in dry steppe slopes under trees in moss, for example in Mykolaiv Region

(Buz'kyi Gard — Krivosheyev, 2015) and Kharkiv Region (Dvorichna National Park — Krivosheyev, 2020), but not in Khmelnytsky Region, so its occurrence in Khmelnytsky Region was assumed and then confirmed. Thus, the area map of this species includes all similar ecosystems of the Dniester River in its entire valley, and could be expected also in Chernivtsi Region and Ivano-Frankivsk Region, which requires additional studies.

Results

Euplectus nanus (Reichenbach, 1816)

Roubal, 1930: 494; ; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 285; Löbl, 2009: 4.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Vrublivtsi, deciduous forest, in litter, 6.06.2017, 48.616948 N, 26.767868 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem,

Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Notes. In dead wood and in litter, sometimes with ants (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995)

***Euplectus kirbii kirbii* Denny, 1825**

Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 285; Löbl, 2009: 4.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Under the bark and in dead wood (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1996b)

***Euplectus frivaldszkyi* Saulcy, 1878**

Roubal, 1930: 493; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 284; Löbl, 2009: 4.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Smotrych river bank, in grass, 8.06.2017, 48.681467 N, 26.578735 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Eastern Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Under the tree bark, sometimes with ants дерев (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

***Trimium brevicorne* (Reichenbach, 1816)**

Roubal, 1930: 490; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 293; Löbl, 2009: 10.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky distr., Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kolodiivka, Rus'ka river bank, dry steppe slopes along the river, 23.04.2023, 48.6085766 N, 26.9422109 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Dobrivliany, mixed forest along the no-named stream, in litter, 27–28.09.2023, 48.6774838 N, 25.7440554 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, steppe and deciduous forest along Strypa river, 1–2.10.2023, 48.874528, 25.420679, 12 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zoloty Potik, deciduous forest along Zolota river, in litter, 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 7 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter and moss (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995)

***Batrisodes adnexus* (Hampe, 1863)**

Roubal, 1930: 499; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 277; Löbl, 2009: 10.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, under the willow stub bark, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK)

Distribution. Europe excl. Spain, Greece, UK and Scandinavia (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Under the bark, often with ants (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995)

***Brachygluta fossulata* (Reichenbach, 1816)**

Roubal, 1930: 500; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 297; Löbl, 2009: 12.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Smotrych river bank, in grass, 8.06.2017, 48.681467 N, 26.578735 E, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Surzhyntsi, deciduous forest, under the bark, 5.06.2017, 48.607797 N, 26.770850 E, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Ushytsa, steppe, Dniester bank, in grass and moss, 20.04.2023, 48.601379 N, 27.113797 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev)

(SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Melnitsa-Podilska, along Dniester, dry forest, 18.05.2023, 48.608362, 26.150748, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kolodribka, along Dniester, steppe slopes, 20–21.05.2023, 48.646124, 26.058138, 3 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 3 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, steppe and deciduous forest along Strypa river, 1–2.10.2023, 48.874528, 25.420679, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, grass, soil, moss and under the bark (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995)

***Brachygluta haematica* (Reichenbach, 1816)**

Roubal, 1930: 501; Kubisz et al., 1998: 234; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 297; Löbl, 2009: 12.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Vrublitski, deciduous forest, in litter, 6.06.2017, 48.616948 N, 26.767868 E, 6 ♂, 3 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 4 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kolodiivka, in moss under blackthorns along Rus'ka river, 22.04.2023, 48.615378 N, 26.935841 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Kolodribka, along Dniester, steppe slopes, 20–21.05.2023, 48.646124 N, 26.058138 E, 6 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Dobrivliany, mixed forest along the no-named stream, in litter, 27–28.09.2023, 48.6774838 N, 25.7440554 E, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK);

Distribution. Europe excl. North (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In moss, grass and litter near the freshwater basins (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995, 1996b).

***Fagniezia impressa* (Panzer, 1805) (fig. 1)**

Roubal, 1930: 502; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 299; Löbl, 2009: 14.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Stinka, deciduous forest along Dniester, 7.10.2023, 48.9137896 N, 25.2353132 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Along the banks of freshwater and saltwater basins in litter, sand and in silt (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

***Rybaxis longicornis* (Leach, 1817)**

Roubal, 1930: 502; Kubisz et al., 1998: 234; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 300; Löbl, 2009: 14.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Stinka, deciduous forest along Dniester, 7.10.2023, 48.9137896 N, 25.2353132 E, 4 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. North (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter, moss and grass along the riverbanks (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995, 1996b).

***Bryaxis carinula* (Rey, 1888)**

Kubisz et al., 1998: 234; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Center and East of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. On the slopes of dry hills and mountains in forests, thermophilic (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Fig. 1. *Fagniezia impressa* (Panzer, 1805), habitus dorsal.

Fig. 2. *Bryaxis cateniger* Krauss, 1899, male habitus dorsal.

Bryaxis puncticollis (Denny, 1825)

Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 309; Löbl, 2009: 20.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dniestrovsky Canyon National Park, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. Greece, Spain and Portugal (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of forests in elevations (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis nigripennis (Aubé, 1844)

Roubal, 1930: 502; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 308; Löbl, 2009: 18.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dniestrovsky Canyon National Park, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 4 ♂, 15 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zoloty Potik, beech forest along Zolota river, in litter 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 10 ♂, 12 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, ravine near Snovidow, forest, in litter, 5.10.2023, 48.908766 N, 25.269305 E, 4 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Stinka, deciduous forest along Dniester, 7.10.2023, 48.9137896 N, 25.2353132 E, 7 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Bryaxis cateniger Krauss, 1899 (fig. 2)

Besuchet, 2004: 304; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Austria, Italy, Slovenia (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter of beech mountain forests (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis ruthenus (Saulcy, 1877)

Roubal, 1930: 507; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 310; Löbl, 2009: 20.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dniestrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 8 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Stinka, deciduous forest along Dniester, 7.10.2023, 48.9137896 N, 25.2353132 E, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Vistria, near Dniester, along the canyon, in moss, 8.10.2023 48.941000 N, 25.147205 E, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Italy (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In litter on the slopes of the mountains (Roubal, 1930).

Bryaxis curtisii (Leach, 1817)

Roubal, 1930: 505; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 305; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Sovyi yar near Studenytsia river, in litter, 7.06.2017, 48.646723 N, 26.883075 E., 5 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Smotrych river bank, in grass, 8.06.2017, 48.681467 N, 26.578735 E, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Vrublivtsi, deciduous forest, in litter, 6.06.2017, 48.616948 N, 26.767868 E, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Surzhyntsi, deciduous forest, under the bark, 5.06.2017, 48.607797 N, 26.770850 E, 1 ♂, 15 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 5 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Goraivka, dry steppe hills along Dniester, 21.04.2023, 48.574567 N, 27.013131 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dniestrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 8 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Dobrivliany, mixed forest along the no-named stream, in litter, 27–28.09.2023, 48.6774838 N, 25.7440554 E, 8 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 15 ♂, 10 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, steppe and

deciduous forest along Strypa river, 1–2.10.2023, 48.874528, 25.420679, 14 ♂, 42 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zoloty Potik, deciduous forest along Zolota river, in litter 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 25 ♂, 34 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, ravine near Snovidow, forest, in litter, 5.10.2023, 48.908766 N, 25.269305 E, 4 ♂, 4 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Stinka, deciduous forest along Dniester, 7.10.2023, 48.9137896 N, 25.2353132 E, 4 ♂, 10 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. North (Löbl, 2004)

Notes. In litter, moss and under the bark of deciduous forests (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis viertli Reitter, 1882

Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 311; Löbl, 2009: 20.

Material examined. Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 2 ♂, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zoloty Potik, deciduous forest along Zolota river, in litter 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 3 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Vistria, near Dniester, along the canyon, in moss, 8.10.2023 48.941000 N, 25.147205 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Ukraine, Hungary, Romania, Serbia and Montenegro (Löbl, 2004; Krivosheyev, 2018).

Notes. In litter and moss of dry hills (Krivosheyev, 2018).

Bryaxis bulbifer (Reichenbach, 1816)

Roubal, 1930: 504; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zoloty Potik, deciduous forest along Zolota river, in litter 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. South (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mesophilic species, occurs in litter under willows and alders near the riverbanks (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis clavicornis (Panzer, 1809)

Roubal, 1930: 504; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304; Löbl, 2009: 16.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Northern and Central Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In forests along the warm slopes of hills and mountains, often in moss and under the logs (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bryaxis chaudiroidii (Chaudiroid, 1845)

Roubal, 1930: 504; Kubisz et al., 1998: 234; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 304.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 2 ♂, 3 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Ushytsa, steppe, Dniester bank, in grass and moss, 20.04.2023, 48.601379 N, 27.113797 E, 5 ♂, 8 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Goraivka, dry steppe hills along Dniester, 21.04.2023, 48.574567 N, 27.013131 E, 4 ♂, 5 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kolodiivka, in moss under blackthorns along Rus'ka river, 22.04.2023, 48.615378 N, 26.935841 E, 9 ♂, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 1 ♂, 6 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 5 ♂, 7 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, steppe and deciduous forest along Strypa river, 1–2.10.2023, 48.874528, 25.420679, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Vistria, near Dniester, along the canyon, in moss, 8.10.2023 48.941000 N, 25.147205 E, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Mediterranean and East of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. In moss and litter under blackthorn and hawthorn bushes along the dry steppe hills (own observations).

Bythinus macropalpus Aubé, 1833

Roubal, 1930: 507; Kubisz et al., 1998: 234; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 312; Löbl, 2009: 22.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Vrublivtsi, deciduous forest, in litter, 6.06.2017, 48.616948 N, 26.767868 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Surzhyntsi, deciduous forest, under the bark, 5.06.2017, 48.607797 N, 26.770850 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kitaigorod, slopes of Tarnava river, cliffs, in moss, 19.04.2023, 48.649496 N, 26.774665 E, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Ushytsa, steppe, Dniester bank, in grass and moss, 20.04.2023, 48.601379 N, 27.113797 E, 3 ♂, 3 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Melnitsa-Podilska, along Dniester, dry forest, 18.05.2023, 48.608362, 26.150748, 4 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Dobrivliany, mixed forest along the no-named stream, in litter, 27–28.09.2023, 48.6774838 N, 25.7440554 E, 2 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, steppe and deciduous forest along Strypa river, 1–2.10.2023, 48.874528, 25.420679, 2 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zoloty Potik, deciduous forest along Zolota river, in litter 3–4.10.2023, 48.873700, 25.326938, 12 ♂, 16 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe, excl. South (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Mesophyllic species, lives nearby the freshwater banks in deciduous forests (Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995).

Bythinus acutangulus Reitter, 1878* (figs 3–4)

Roubal, 1930: 507; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 311; Löbl, 2009: 20.

Material examined. Ukraine, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, ravine near Snovidow, forest, in litter, 5.10.2023, 48.908766 N, 25.269305 E, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Bulgaria, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, Macedonia, Bosnia and Herzegovina (Löbl, 2004); Ukraine (first record).

Notes. In litter of deciduous forests (own observations).

Tychus niger (Paykull, 1800) (fig. 5)

Roubal, 1930: 508; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 320; Löbl, 2009: 22.

Material examined. Ukraine, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Melnitsa-Podilska, along Dniester, dry forest, 18.05.2023, 48.608362, 26.150748, 2 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Almost whole of Europe (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Along the freshwater banks in litter (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995, 1996b).

Pselaphus heisei (Herbst, 1792)

Roubal, 1930: 508; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 327; Löbl, 2009: 24.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnytsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Ushytsa, steppe, Dniester bank, in grass and moss, 20.04.2023, 48.601379 N, 27.113797 E, 10 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Goraivka, dry steppe hills along Dniester, 21.04.2023, 48.574567 N, 27.013131 E, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Kolodiivka, in moss under blackthorns along Rus'ka river, 22.04.2023, 48.615378 N, 26.935841 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 5 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, ravine near Snovidow, forest, in litter, 5.10.2023, 48.908766 N, 25.269305 E, 2 specimens (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); idem, Vistria, near Dniester, along

Figs 3-4. *Bythinus acutangulus* Reitter, 1878: 3 - male habitus dorsal; 4 - aedeagus.

Fig. 5. *Tychus niger* (Paykull, 1800), male habitus dorsal.

Fig. 6. *Pselaphus salonitanus* (Karaman, 1940), habitus dorsal.

the canyon, in moss, 8.10.2023 48.941000 N, 25.147205 E, 1 specimen (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

***Pselaphus salonitanus* (Karaman, 1940)* (fig. 6)**

Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 327.

Material examined. Ukraine, Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, vicinity of Nyrkiv, Dzurin river valley, hornbeam forest, in litter, 29–30.09.2023, 48.805097, 25.585033, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Croatia, Italy (Löbl, 2004); Ukraine (first record).

Notes. The only female of the species was found in moss near the Dzhurin waterfall on a dry steppe hill. The species differs from *P. heisei* by smaller size (1.6 mm), brighter body colour and shine, narrower and more elongate abdomen, and shorter antennae: in *P. heisei* antennomeres 3 to 7 are elongate and 8 is square, whereas in *P. salonitanus* the antennomeres are square. The species was identified using the keys by Reitter (1881) and Karaman (1940).

***Claviger testaceus* Preyssler, 1790 (fig. 7)**

Roubal, 1930: 510; Löbl, Besuchet, 2004: 282; Löbl, 2009: 24.

Material examined. Ukraine, Khmelnitsky Region, Podilski Tovtry National Park, Kolodiivka, under stones with *Lasius flavus* Fabricius, 1781, 22.04.2023, 48.615378 N, 26.935841 E, 3 ♂, 1 ♀ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK); Ternopil Region, Dnistrovsky Canyon National Park, Zalischiky, dry deciduous forest along Dniester, in moss, 21.05.2023, 48.6397145 N, 25.7300311 E, 1 ♂ (Krivosheyev) (SIZK).

Distribution. Europe excl. Finland (Löbl, 2004).

Notes. Myrmecophilic species, lives under stones in dry steppe slopes (Roubal, 1930; Neuhäuser-Happe, 1995, 1996b).

Fig. 7. *Claviger testaceus* Preyssler, 1790, male habitus dorsal

Conclusion

As a result, *Euplectus nanus*, *Euplectus kirbii kirbii*, and *Batrissodes adnexus* are recorded for the first time from Kmelnitsky Region, *Fagniezia impressa*, *Bryaxis ruthenus*, and *Tychus niger* — from Ternopil Region, *Claviger testaceus* — from both Khmelnitsky and Ternopil Region, and *Bythinus acutangulus* and *Pselaphus salonitanus* — from Ukraine (*).

Acknowledgements

I thank Mykhaylo Drebet from Podilski Tovtry National Nature Park and Olexandr Vikirchak from Dniester Canyon National Nature Park, for their kind assistance during expeditions and material gathering, and Viktor Fursov (I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology) for help in taking microphotographies.

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